

ISic0836

I.Sicily inscription 0836

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κεῖτε
2. Ἄγαματις καὶ
3. Τριανὸς δοῦλο[ι]
4. Σοφίας λαμωπρ
5. [οτάτης γυναικός]

Apparatus

Text from IG

Kaibel suggests Πρίαμος or Τριάριος for Τριανὸς

Kaibel suggests that Caietanus misread the maiscule form μ on the stone as a ω

Translation (it)

Translation (en)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492464

EDCS 39101990

PHI 140313

Bibliography

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